

Maryam Mokhtari Dinani, Hashem Kouzechian, Abbas Nazarian Madavani. (2015). [The relationship between Organizational Intelligence and leadership effectiveness of sport managers](#), [New trends in sports management](#), 3 (9): 31-41.

The relationship between organizational intelligence and leadership effectiveness of sport managers

Maryam Mokhtari Dinani¹- Hashem Kozechian- Abbas Nazarian Madavani²

Abstract

Leadership effectiveness is a factor of successful in any organizations. Hence, it is important to identification of factors that can be related to this factor. Therefore, the purpose of this research was to investigate the relationship between organizational intelligence and leadership effectiveness of sport managers. The Statistical popularly was all managers of Sport and Young's Ministry, National Olympic committee, National Paralympics committee, National Olympic Academy, and Sport Federations (N=331). Base on Morgan table, 180 people were selected to this research. Leadership effectiveness questionnaire, and Karl Albrecht (2003) organizational intelligence questionnaire was used to collect data. Data analysis was performed by the multivariate regression. The results of present study showed that there was significant relationship between leadership effectiveness and organizational intelligence ($p<0/05$). Also, there were significant relationships between Heart, Alignment congruence and Performance pressure with leadership effectiveness ($p<0/05$). Generally, this study showed that organizational intelligence is important factor in leadership effectiveness of sport managers.

Key words: Alignment congruence, Effectiveness, Heart, Leadership, Intelligence

¹ . Assistant Professor of Alzahra University, Email: M.mokhtaridinani@Alzahra.ac.ir

² . Assistant Professor of Shahid Rajaei University, Email: Abbasnazarian@Sru.ac.ir